

ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS: A CASE STUDY OF UNIVERSITY OF KASHMIR

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Abstract:

Entrepreneurship is considered as an important factor not only in the economic development of nations but also in the development of humans. Entrepreneurship is the single potential source of employment which can address the burgeoning problem of unemployment of youth, particularly in developing countries like India. India with higher rate of unemployment, it is all the more necessary to foster entrepreneurship. For entrepreneurial development among the other factors which lead to entrepreneurship development, education is believed to play a vital role. As such, it becomes imperative to study and know what drives a student towards entrepreneurship and establishment of new ventures. Therefore, this case study explores the entrepreneurial intentions of students of university of Kashmir and also studies the influence of the students' participation in entrepreneurship education programmes on their entrepreneurial intentions. This study is conducted with the purpose to contribute towards the improvement of entrepreneurship education in Jammu and Kashmir.

Key words: *Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Entrepreneurship education, Venture Creation, Social Norms*

INTRODUCTION:

Entrepreneurship is considered to be an important factor for economic and human development. Various public, private and governmental organizations across the globe are taking measures to promote entrepreneurship. An important role generally associated with entrepreneurship is promoting economic activity (European Commission 2003). It has been reported that there have been significant decreases in unemployment levels in regions where entrepreneurial activities have flourished (Audretsch, 2002). Therefore, there is a general consensus among researchers about the importance of promoting entrepreneurship to stimulate economic development and employment generation. Therefore entrepreneurship is becoming a popular career choice (van Gelderen et al., 2008) and is being promoted as an attractive career alternative among students all over the world (Schwarz et al., 2009). In India also there have been a number of initiatives to encourage entrepreneurial activity among youth as it is facing higher rate of unemployment which makes it all the more necessary to foster entrepreneurship development. This is facilitated by the agreement of researchers that entrepreneurs are made and not born (Boulton and Turner, 2005; Mellor et al., 2009), inferring that entrepreneurs can actually be trained. Therefore, it becomes imperative to identify factors that make an entrepreneur and the issues related to the development of entrepreneurs. (Kadir et al., 2011). Studies have reported that entrepreneurial activities are based on intentions (Krueger et al., 2000). Hence it can be surmised that people's decision to become entrepreneurs are based on certain triggers of which the most important is intention.

A number of works have been carried out which show that entrepreneurship education programs contribute to the development of entrepreneurial intentions (Izquierdo & Buelens, 2008, Lüthje & Franke, 2003, Peterman and Kennedy, 2003, Kolvereid & Moens, 1997, Souitaris et al., 2007, Fayolle et al., 2006). Many Universities and colleges have introduced and implemented courses in small business management and entrepreneurship. In India, a number of universities and vocational training institutes have implemented entrepreneurship and small business

management courses to expose students in starting their own ventures. There is a general acceptance that the present educational system of higher educational institutions has to impart entrepreneurial and industrial exposure to students so that they become change agents for creating enterprises. Even now, fostering innovations and new product development through entrepreneurship has not been regarded as a crucial task of universities (Mohammad & Aparna, 2011).

Review of Literature

To better understand entrepreneurial behaviour the review provides some highlights of previous research on entrepreneurial intentions. Intention stems from intentionality, which is defined as a state of mind which directs a person's attention toward a specific goal in order to achieve something. Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, (2000) concur that the process of entrepreneurship is a way of thinking with its emphasis on opportunities rather than threats. A number of intention models have been developed in previous researches. Peterman and Kennedy (2003) note that majority of models on entrepreneurial intention make use of attitude and behaviour theory (Ajzen, 1991) and self-efficacy and social learning theory (Bandura, 1997). A number of other have been developed which include Shapero's model (1975) which was tested by Krueger (1993), on the influence of desirability and feasibility to a business start-up. Bird (1988) suggested a model of intentional action, and more recently Lüthje and Franke (2003) proposed a structural model of entrepreneurial intent. Entrepreneurial intention has been a leading construct within the entrepreneurship literature over the last few decades (Moiz)). A number of studies have explored the causes of entrepreneurial propensity (Greenberger and Sexton, 1988; Learned, 1992) only a limited number of studies has focused on the entrepreneurial intent among students.(Luthje & Franke)

The significance of entrepreneurship education has been felt owing to amplified need in preparing students to cope in the present-day work and living environment. An increasing need has been filled to hone students from any specialization apart from business management to gain a sense of initiative and enterprising character as a key competency necessary for all. Entrepreneurship education has been defined both broadly and in narrower terms. Kourilsky, (1995) referred from Jones & English(2004) defines Entrepreneurship education as "Opportunity recognition, marshalling of resources in the presence of risk, and building a business venture". Another definition by Bechard & Toulouse, (1998) states entrepreneurship education as "a collection of formalised teachings that informs, trains, and educates anyone interested in business creation, or small business development". There is currently a strong global drive towards encouraging a greater proportion of students to consider and pursue venture creation as an alternative graduate career path (Nabi, 2006; Leffel & Darling, 2009). As a result of this viewpoint, many authors have studied factors influencing students' entrepreneurial career intentions and motivations in both developed and developing countries (e.g. Kolvereid, 1996; Carter et al., 2003) as well as the role of higher education institutions in the promotion of entrepreneurial initiative among students (Autio et al., 1997, 2001; Fayolle, Gailly, & Lassas-Clerc, 2006). Policy makers deem that increased levels of entrepreneurship can be reached through education (European Commission, 2006) more so entrepreneurship education. Hence many European countries have introduced such type of education in their course curriculum. (European Commission, 2006). McMullan & Long, (1987) surmise that entrepreneurship education is a significant constituent of economic strategies for fostering job creation. Vesper (1990) in his study found out that entrepreneurial awareness is facilitated by University educators. Potter 2008 goes a step further in defining the role of entrepreneurship education as one of the most important factor in increasing the entrepreneurial attitude of people. Thus, educational initiatives have been considered as highly promising to increase the supply of potential entrepreneurs (that is to say, making more people aware and interested on this career option) and of nascent entrepreneurs (making more people try to start a new venture). linan et al(2010)

Objectives

In order to carry out the study and to understand attitude of the students towards entrepreneurship, the following specific objectives were laid down

1. To study the attitude of University students towards entrepreneurship.
2. To study the differences among male and female students towards entrepreneurship and willingness to start their own venture.
3. To study the differences among students' preference towards government jobs and private jobs.

Method

The present case study to assess entrepreneurship attitude among students, has been conducted on the students of University of Kashmir. For the purpose of primary data collection, a sample of 133 students was drawn randomly from the current students of the university. The survey was conducted with the help of self administered close ended questionnaire which were filled by the student respondents. Out of 135 questionnaires that were sent, two questionnaires were incompletely filled by the respondents and hence were dropped from the study. This yielded a high response rate of 98.5 per cent. This high response rate can be attributed to the fact that the questionnaires were personally distributed by the researchers. The questionnaire used for the study consists of demographic variables in the first part. The demographic variables included gender, marital status, age and present occupation of the respondents. The second part consists of question related to six constructs: Personal Attraction (8 items), Entrepreneurial Intentions, (2 items) Entrepreneurship Experience (4 items), Participation in Entrepreneurship Education (2 items). Respondents were asked to indicate their degree of agreement or disagreement with each statement on a five-point Likert scale, from strongly agree to strongly disagree for variable Personal attraction(Attitude), while for the rest of the items dichotomous scale (Yes/No) have been used.

Table 5.1: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.no			Freq	%
1.	Gender	Male	64	48.9
		Female	67	51.1
2.	Marital Status	Married	2	1.5
		Unmarried	129	98.5
3.	Age	>20	15	11.5
		20-21	14	10.7
		22-23	61	46.6
		24-25	20	15.3
		<25	21	16.0
4.	Presently self employed	Yes	6.8%	
		No	93.2%	

The Table 5.1 shows the composition and characteristics of the sample of the study. For the purpose of study, students from Kashmir University were selected. As is evident from the table, 48.9% of the respondents were males and 51.1% were females. As only students were included in the sample, so it can be seen that majority i.e 98.5 % of the respondents was unmarried. The age profile indicates that 11.5 % respondents were less than 20 years , 10.7%

were between 20-21 years, 46.6% belong to 22-23 years age group, 15.3% were between 23-24 years while 16 % were more than 25 years old. 6.8% students were self employed as against 93.2% respondents who indicated that they were not working anywhere as part time or in any sort of employment.

Analysis and Interpretation

The data collected were systematically processed and made suitable for analysis purpose. The data were classified, tabulated and the analyses like descriptive analysis, t Test, were performed to arrive at valid conclusions.

Table 5.2: Career Preferences

Career preference	Freq	%
govt job	69	52.7
private	15	11.5
liberal	13	9.9
entrepreneur	28	21.4

As far as career preferences among youth are considered table 5.2 depicts that 52.7 % students prefer government jobs, 11.5 % prefer private job, 9.9% liberal profession, 21.4% entrepreneurship and 4.6% preferred to become freelancers. The preference for govt. job by majority of the students is a reflection of the fact that presently, the most preferred job in the region is govt. job. Hence this trend may be related to the present culture.

Table 5.3: Entrepreneurial Intentions

S.no	Item	Yes	No
1	plan to be self employed in future	69.5	30.5
2	Participated in entrepreneurship education	25.2	74.8
3	Participated in entrepreneurship education in University of Kashmir	16.0	84.0
4	Parents ever started a business	51.8	48.2
5	Any one you know started a business	78.6	21.4
6	Ever worked for a small or new company	16.8	83.2
7	Have you ever started a new business	12.2	87.8

The table 5.3 depicts the intention of students to become self employed in future. It reports that 69.5% students would like to be self employed which signifies a shift in mindset of youth from existing preference for govt jobs. While 25.2% students have participated in entrepreneurship education,16% students have received entrepreneurship education in Kashmir University whereas 51.8% students indicated that their parents have started a business, 78.6% students reported that they have friends and relatives who have started their own ventures. Further 83.2% of the respondents reported that they have never worked for a small or new company, as against this 12.2% students indicated that they have started their own business.

Table.5.4 : Entrepreneurial Attitude

S.No.	Item	M	S.D
1	Entrepreneurs are always born	2.5	1.39
2	Entrepreneurship is a better career	3.4	1.23
3	Entrepreneurship has more charms than challenges	2.9	1.43
4	I will start a firm	3.8	1.52
5	Graduates prefer to become entrepreneurs	2.8	1.32
6	Entrepreneurship gives more satisfaction than other professions.	3.3	1.30
7	I am self motivated towards entrepreneurship	3.1	1.37
8	Job advertisement doesn't convince me to apply for it	2.6	1.42

The table 5.4 exhibits the respondents' attitude towards entrepreneurship. As can be seen from the table, mean score for item no.1 is 2.5 which indicate that students don't agree that entrepreneurs are only born. Regarding whether entrepreneurship is a better career option than others, the mean score of 3.4 for this indicates that students have a high agreement with the statement. When asked whether entrepreneurship entailed greater charms than challenges, the mean score obtained was 2.9 which indicates that respondents agree with the statement. As far as establishment of their own ventures are concerned, the mean score obtained was 3.8 which indicates that students have a high propensity to start their own firm. Mean score obtained for item no. 5 is 2.8 which shows that respondents somewhat agree that graduates prefer to become entrepreneurs. When asked whether students don't readily apply for jobs in comparison to pursuing entrepreneurship, mean score obtained is 2.6 which show that students have greater preference for government jobs, which may again be linked to cultural factors and limitations in the external environment and infrastructure.

Table 5.5 : Impact of gender on entrepreneurial attitude

S.no	Item	Males		Females		Mean Diff	t-value	sig
		M	S.D	M	S.D			
1	Entrepreneurs are always born	2.84	1.43	2.13	1.26	.70	2.92	.00*
2	Entrepreneurship is a better career	3.50	1.24	3.16	1.21	.33	1.56	.12
3	Entrepreneurship has more charms than challenges	2.96	1.33	2.82	1.53	.14	.58	.55
4	I will start a firm	4.23	1.15	3.32	1.70	.90	3.55	.00*
5	Graduates prefer to become entrepreneurs	2.87	1.26	2.82	1.39	.05	.23	.81
6	Entrepreneurship gives more satisfaction other professions.	3.51	1.30	3.10	1.28	.41	1.81	.07
7	I am self motivated towards entrepreneurship	3.28	1.25	3.00	1.48	.28	1.16	.24
8	Job advertisement doesn't convince me to apply for it	2.64	1.39	2.62	1.45	.01	.05	.95

In order to understand the difference in attitude of males and females towards entrepreneurship, t-test was conducted to ascertain whether there were significant differences in the perception of male and female students towards entrepreneurship attitude. As can be seen from the table, there is significant difference between male and female respondents regarding the item “Entrepreneurs are always born”. Similar results have been obtained for variable 4 wherein respondents were asked about willingness in starting their own firm. In rest of the items, no significant difference was found. Thus it can be concluded that entrepreneurship can emerge as a viable career option equally for both males and females with a little bit of difference in training and support.

Table-5.6 : Job preference and entrepreneurship attitude

S.No.	Item	Govt job		Private job		Mean Diff	t- value	Sig
		M	S.D	M	S.D			
1	Entrepreneurs are always born	2.49	1.27	2.60	1.35	-.10	-.29	.77
2	Entrepreneurship is a better career	3.21	1.24	3.46	1.06	-.24	-.719	.47
3	Entrepreneurship has more charms than challenges	2.76	1.37	3.00	1.41	-.23	-.59	.55
4	I will start a firm	3.59	1.55	4.13	1.35	-.53	-1.24	.21
5	Graduates prefer to become entrepreneurs	2.66	1.24	2.66	1.29	.00	.00	1.00
6	Entrepreneurship gives more satisfaction than other professions.	3.20	1.36	3.66	1.29	-.46	-1.20	.23
7	I am self motivated towards entrepreneurship	3.05	1.34	3.46	1.40	-.40	-1.05	.29
8	Job advertisement doesn't convince me to apply for it	2.42	1.37	2.80	1.37	-.37	-.96	.33

Mean (M), Standard Deviation (S.D) and t-values for Govt and private Jobs

The common notion that those who prefer private job prefer entrepreneurship more than those who prefer govt jobs was tested with the help of t test. T- Test was conducted for two groups one who preferred government jobs and second who preferred private jobs to ascertain whether there are significant differences in these two groups towards attitude to entrepreneurship. As can be seen from the table, there exists no significant difference between students whose career preference is either government job or private job towards entrepreneurship attitude. This again points to the fact that lack of opportunities and facilities make students to prefer job over entrepreneurship.

Findings

The objective of the study was to assess the intention of youth towards entrepreneurship as a career option. The analysis presents certain findings.

1. Majority of the students (69.5%) indicated their preference for self employment. This shows a growing trend of students towards entrepreneurship.
2. The participation of students in entrepreneurship education is in a lower side as the results obtained were 25.2% which is further even lower for entrepreneurship education at University of Kashmir at 16%. This is a barrier as non

participation of students towards entrepreneurship courses may result in decreased propensity to start up their own ventures.

3. As for the variable social norms, a high score was obtained which indicates the influence of their parents or friends who are entrepreneurs. The ‘reference people’ have a positive impact on the perceptions of students to pursue entrepreneurship.

4. For the variable entrepreneurship experience, low scores have been obtained which indicate that majority of students don’t have experience of working in a new firm or starting up a new venture.

5. On the variable ‘personal attraction’ with 8 items, the highest mean score was obtained for the statement “ I will start a firm” followed by the statement “ Entrepreneurship is a better career option” which indicates that students have a high intention of starting their own businesses.

6. With regard to the differences among male and female students towards entrepreneurship and willingness to start their own venture, much difference was not reported which indicate that both can be targeted for entrepreneurship.

7. Preference for entrepreneurship was found similar in those who prefer govt. job or private job, as t test found no significant differences between the two groups of respondents.

Implications

As can be inferred from the findings, majority of the students have a preference for pursuing entrepreneurship as a career, which has some implications for the policy makers, educational institutions and the society as a whole:

1. Students’ inclination towards entrepreneurship should be properly honed and channelled by family as well as educational institutions so that students can become successful entrepreneurs.

2. University should introduce courses in Entrepreneurship education as this will increase the propensity of students in starting their own ventures.

3. Educational institutes should create an ‘entrepreneurial atmosphere’ which will improve the image of entrepreneurship as a viable career alternative.

4. Government should introduce programmes and schemes for supporting entrepreneurship as this will help in curbing the menace of unemployment in the state.

5. Female students have equal inclination towards entrepreneurship so Govt should also focus efforts on women entrepreneurship.

Conclusions

The objective of this paper was to contribute to an improvement of entrepreneurship education in the state of Jammu and Kashmir. To achieve this, the study explored the entrepreneurial intentions among Kashmir University students. The analysis confirms many previous findings in literature on students’ entrepreneurial intentions. The study shows that students prefer to become entrepreneurs. This inclination towards entrepreneurship is same among male and female students.

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